

Speculation on Transition Rate Between Different Energy Levels of an Atom

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In previous notes, we noted that the wavefunction of an excited state may be written as: $W_n(x) = W_0(x)W_1(x)$ and a differential equation for $W_1(x)$ found, with $V(x)$ removed but $W_0(x)$, the ground state present. This DE is sometimes simpler to solve than the Schrodinger equation if one is able to find $W_0(x)$ by inspection. In this note, we calculate the entropy of $W_0(x)W_1(x)$ speculating that $W_1(x)$ may have physical relevance because a photon/phonon is readily absorbed or emitted. Thus given $W_n(x)$, it may be replaced by $W_{n-1}(x)W_a(x)$ or $W_{n-2}(x)W_b(x)$... to $W_0(x)W_1(x)$. Using a formula we suggested in (1), entropy for the various scenarios may be found and these may be linked to the probability of decay from W_n to $W_{n-1}(x)$ versus say $W_i(x)$. This approach is speculative as there is no guarantee that $W_1(x)$ is physical. Traditionally, it seems one uses a perturbative potential and calculates coupling between different excited states, but this suggests knowing the perturbative potential, with different potentials leading to different transition rates. We examine the case of a quantum oscillator as an example, but stress that the calculation is a crude estimate and the procedure speculative.

General Scheme of Added Velocities

The idea of utilizing $W_n(x) = W_0(x)W_1(x)$ or another factoring scheme in order to obtain an equation with the potential removed already appears in classical mechanics. For instance, consider: $m/2 v(x)v(x) + V(x) = E_n$, where E_n is a particular energy value and $v(x)$ its corresponding velocity. If one changes energy to $E_n + b$, then $V(x)$ remains the same at each x point, so there is an extra kinetic energy of b at each x . " $v(x)$ " becomes $v(x) + v_1(x)$ such that:

$$m/2 v_1(x)v_1(x) + m v_1(x)v(x) = b \quad ((1))$$

The same result holds in a quantum bound state for $W_n(x) = W_0(x)W_1(x)$ except for the fact that ensemble averages $\langle v_0^*v_0 \rangle$ and $\langle v_1^*v_1 \rangle$ are used i.e.

$$-1/2m d/dx d/dx W_1(x) - 1/m dW_0/dx dW_1/dx = b \quad ((2))$$

Here $W_0(x)$ is the ground state (or an excited state which is in resonance) so one may speculate that $W_1(x)$ has physical meaning in that a photon/phonon may be absorbed or emitted readily. In particular, we suggest one may calculate entropy values for various $W_n = W_i W_j$ situations where W_i is the ground or an excited state and W_j is the remaining function needed.

This may shed light on whether a state W_n is metastable due to entropy considerations as well as suggesting which transitions are more likely.

Entropy of $W_0(x)W_1(x)$

In (1), we suggested that Shannon's entropy for $W(x)$ is given by:

$$S = -\sum_{x, p_1, p_2} a(p_1)a(p_2) \exp(i(p_1+p_2)x) \ln[a(p_1)a(p_2) \exp(i(p_1+p_2)x)] \quad ((3))$$

$$= -\sum_{x, p} W(x) \frac{d}{dx} W(x) - \sum_{p} a(p)a(-p) \ln[a(p)a(-p)] \quad \text{A } 2\pi \text{ is absorbed into } a(p)a(-p)$$

The integral of the first term yields 1, but the second term gives a nonconstant value. The probability used in evaluating Shannon's entropy in ((3)) arises from terms used to create the spatial density i.e. $W(x)W(x) = \sum_{p_1, p_2} a(p_1)\exp(ip_1x) a(p_2)\exp(ip_2x)$

For the case of $W_0(x)W_1(x)$:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Entropy} = & \left\{ \sum_{x, p} -W_1(x)W_1(x) \frac{d}{dx} W_0 + W_0W_0 \frac{d}{dx} W_1 \right\} \\ & + \sum_{p, p'} a(p) \ln[a(p)] - W_0W_0W_1 \exp(ipx) \sum_{p'} b(p') \ln[b(p')] \end{aligned} \quad ((4))$$

where $a(p)$ is associated with the Fourier transform of $W_0(x)$ and $b(p)$ with $W_1(x)$. The first term again integrates to 1 because $W_0W_0W_1W_1$ is normalized to 1.

As a result, ((4)) yields a formula for calculating entropies of different product combinations creating a particular $W_n(x)$. One may thus compare the entropy for different W_0W_1 combinations such that W_0 is an eigenstate and W_0W_1 a higher energy eigenstate.

It may be noted that the entropy for W_n may be written as:

$$S = 1 - \int dp c(p)c(-p) \ln[c(p)c(-p)] \quad \text{where } c(p) \text{ is associated with the Fourier transform of } W_n. \text{ If } W_n = W_0W_1, \text{ then it seems that } c(p) \text{ is not equal to } a(p)b(p) \text{ where } a(p) \text{ is the Fourier transform of } W_0 \text{ and } b(p) \text{ that of } W_1.$$

In the literature, the expression $-W \ln[W]$ ((4b)) is sometimes used to describe entropy density of a bound particle, but this yields a very different result from that of ((3)). For ((4b)), there is no difference in entropy if one uses $W = W_0W_1$ or $W = W_2W_3$ etc.

Quantum Oscillator Example In Large n Limit

We use the example of a quantum oscillator because the integral over dx of $-W \ln[W]$ and the integral over dp of $-a(p)a(-p) \ln[a(p)a(-p)]$ are essentially the same or at least related (see (2)) i.e. we assume that they are the same with respect to the behaviour of n . We consider the case of large n because one may then use the classical approximation:

$$W_n W_n = C/v_n(x) \quad \text{where } v_n(x) \text{ is velocity taken from: } \frac{m}{2} v_n(x)v_n(x) + \frac{1}{2} kx^2 = E_n \quad ((5))$$

We evaluate $\int \psi^* \psi \ln[\psi^* \psi]$ type integrals instead of the momentum ones to estimate differences in entropy.

The main feature of such an integral is that: $\psi(x) = \sqrt{\frac{2m}{\pi \hbar^2 (E - \frac{1}{2} k x^2)}}$ so one may change variables using: $\sqrt{\frac{1}{2} k} x = \sqrt{E} \sin(a)$. Then C is a constant not related to n , ψ is proportional to $\sqrt{\frac{2m}{\pi \hbar^2}} \sqrt{E} \cos(a)$ and dx is proportional to $\sqrt{E} \cos(a) da$. Thus:

$$\int dx \frac{C}{\psi(x)} = 1$$

Consider two examples:

Case 1 $W_n = W_{n-1}$ [W_n/W_{n-1}] In this case, [W_n/W_{n-1}] is approximately equal to 1 because n is very large and so the entropy should be very similar to that of W_n . The term from ((3)):

$-\frac{1}{W_1} \int \psi_1^* \psi_1 \ln[\psi_1^* \psi_1]$ with $W_1=1$ yields the entropy ((2)) for W_0 which is almost W_n , so the term $-\frac{1}{W_0} \int \psi_0^* \psi_0 \ln[\psi_0^* \psi_0]$ should be almost 0. The term may be considered another way: W_1/W_1 is almost 1

W_0 brings in a factor of $1/\sqrt[4]{E}$, $a(p)$ brings in $1/\sqrt[4]{E}$ (it is the Fourier transform of W_0), dx brings in \sqrt{E} and $\ln(a(p))$ brings in a term $2 \ln(\sqrt[4]{E})$. Thus, the overall effect is: $\ln(\sqrt{n})$.

For the next term from ((3)), W_0/W_1 brings in $1/\sqrt{E}$ from W_0/W_1 , \sqrt{E} from dx and no n related factor from $b(p)$. Thus, the second term is negligible compared to the first.

Using the high n classical limit, the entropy of $a(p)a(p) \ln(a(p))$ may be replaced with: $W(x)W(x) \ln(W(x))$ which for $W(x)W(x) = C/\psi(x)$ yields a result of the order of $\ln(\sqrt{n})$.

If one considers this more carefully, W_1/W_1 is slightly higher than 1 i.e. $\sqrt{E - \frac{1}{2} k x^2} / \sqrt{E - \frac{1}{2} k x^2}$. Thus, entropy is closer to $\frac{d}{2} \ln(\sqrt{n-1})$ where d is slightly larger than 1. If one divides this by the entropy for a pure state W_n (i.e. $\ln(\sqrt{n})$), one obtains:

$(\frac{d-1}{2}) \ln(n) - \frac{d}{2n}$ For n large, the second term disappears and the first remains. Thus, there is a small increase in entropy if the pure state W_n behaves as W_{n-1} [W_n/W_{n-1}] i.e. W_n seems to be metastable. There seems to be an entropy gain if the W_n state is composed of a W_{n-1} state and a W_1 factor i.e. an entropy gain to drop to state $n-1$. Thus, state W_n is metastable.

Case 2 $W_n = W_{n/2}$ [$W_n/W_{n/2}$] = $W_0 W_1$

Calculating entropy seems to be tricky because $b(p)$ is not the Fourier transform of a solution of the oscillator i.e. $W_n/(W_{n/2})$ is not an oscillator wavefunction. We try to obtain an estimate.

Consider the term: $-\sum_p W_1 W_0 \exp(ipx) a(p) \ln[a(p)]$.

In this case, $\sqrt{E_n/2}$ terms are used. W_0 yields $1/\sqrt[4]{E_n/2}$ and $dx \sqrt{E_n/2}$.

The term $a(p)$ brings in $1/\sqrt[4]{E_n/2}$ and $2\ln(a(p))$ yields $-2(.25) \ln(\sqrt{n/2})$ as a dominant term for n high. Here W_0 is a solution of the quantum oscillator for $n/2$ and $a(p)$ is its Fourier transform. For the oscillator case, these two are related, so $\sum_p a(p) \ln(a(p))$ is related to $\int dx W_0 \ln(W_0)$. Thus, knowing the dependence of this integral with respect to n , gives information about the former sum (see (2)).

$W_1 = W_n / W_{n/2} = \sqrt{C/C * v(n/2)(x)/v_n(x)}$ so $W_1 W_0$ this may be estimated as:

$\sqrt{2 - \sin a} / \sqrt{1 - \sin a}$. The numerator brings a factor of $\sqrt{1.5}$ as a crude estimate.

The overall effect is $\ln(\sqrt{n/2}) \sqrt{1.5}$ for the first momentum term of ((3)).

The second term is $\sum_p W_1 W_0 \exp(ipx) b(p) \ln(b(p))$.

W_0 brings in $1/\sqrt{E_n/2}$ and $dx \sqrt{E_n/2}$ so n dependence cancels. W_1 has no n dependence because it is proportional to $\sqrt{E_n/2 - .5kxx} / \sqrt{E_n - .5kxx}$. A $\sqrt{n/2}$ from the numerator and denominator cancel.

$b(p)$ also contains no n dependence because: $W_1 = \sum_p b(p) \exp(ipx)$. Thus, the second term brings in no n dependence and the overall entropy for case 2 seems to be of the order $\sqrt{1.5} \ln(\sqrt{n/2})$.

Comparisons

We find that for an electron dropping to state $n/2$, the total entropy is of the order $\sqrt{1.5} \ln(\sqrt{n/2})$ while it is $\ln(\sqrt{n})$ for the case of dropping from n to $n-1$. Thus, this seems to favor a larger jump. Using $n=100$, one finds that $\ln(\sqrt{100})=2.3$ and $\sqrt{1.5} \ln(\sqrt{50}) = 2.379$, thus there is a small increase in entropy between a jump to the state $n/2$ than for staying in W_n . Next, compare jumping from n to $n-1$ versus to $n/2$. $d \ln(\sqrt{100}) = d * 2.3$. "d" is only slightly larger than 1, so it seems it is preferable to have a larger drop in energy level. For example, for $n=100$, an estimate for d is $\sqrt{100}/\sqrt{99}=1.005$ and $2.3 * 1.005 = 2.3115 < 2.379$.

According to the above crude estimates, dropping to a state $n/3$ would yield an entropy going as: $\sqrt{2.5} \ln(\sqrt{n/3})$. For $n=100$, this yields 2.77 which is higher than the $n/2$ case. Thus, the above estimates seem to favor electron drops to lower energy levels.

The entropy differences are small, but if one uses $\text{Probability} = \exp(\text{entropy})$, then larger effects arise.

A numerical calculation would yield better results.

Implications

In the literature, there are calculations for the entropy of a bound state wavefunction. We give ((3)) and ((4)) as formulae for such cases. For systems with many electrons in various bound states of an atom with a temperature, one simply counts possible positions of the electron without any consideration of an intrinsic entropy of the bound state itself. It seems the entropy of the bound state should somehow be incorporated into the calculation.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we speculate that if one writes $W_n(x) = W_i(x)W_1(x)$ where $W_i(x)$ is a lower energy bound state than $W_n(x)$, one may calculate the entropy for $W_i(x)W_1(x)$ versus W_n and also versus $W_j(x)W_2(x) = W_n(x)$ (where W_j is a different lower energy bound state) and compare the values. We argue that writing the wavefunction as a product may have physical meaning because a photon/phonon may be absorbed or emitted easily. Using the quantum oscillator for high n values as an example, we crudely estimate that the entropy to essentially stay in state n is slightly lower than to have it drop to $n-1$ (for high n) (both are of the order of $\ln(\sqrt{n})$), while the entropy to drop to state $n/2$ is of the order $\sqrt{1.5}\ln(\sqrt{n/2})$. We find that for $n=100$ (quantum oscillator) there is an entropy increase if a particle in state n drops to a lower state. We also find that there is higher entropy for dropping to $n/2$ than for $n-1$. Thus, we argue there is an entropy argument for excited states being metastable.

References

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